

Meta-learning guided Few-shot Learning Method for Gearbox Fault Diagnosis under Limited Data Conditions

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Abstract. Recently, intelligent fault diagnosis technology based on deep learning has been extensively researched and applied in large industrial equipment system for ensuring safe and stable production. However, these deep models only effective when enough data for each observed failure category are available in the training durations. Otherwise, the performance of these models will notably decrease. As the critical component in large machinery, the gearbox often changes the speed and load along with the production demand in the practical application, which caused few data samples to be collected at certain conditions. This phenomenon introduces the few-shot fault diagnosis, and its goal is to identify the fault types with extremely limited data samples. To address this problem, a Meta-learning guided Few-shot Fault Diagnosis method, named MFFD, is proposed for gearbox fault diagnosis under limited data conditions. The results verify the effectiveness of our MFFD method at one-shot and five-shot fault diagnosis tasks under different speed and load conditions.

Keywords: Meta-learning · Few-shot learning · Fault diagnosis · Gearbox · Limited data samples.

1 Introduction

As the critical technology of Prognostic and Health Management (PHM), fault diagnosis aims at identifying failure attribution accurately, thus decide on actions to prevent their occurrence in preventive maintenance. Since the machinery equipment is developed toward high-speed and complexity in recent years, meanwhile, it also needs to meet the needs of health, stable and long-term running, fault diagnosis has become an indispensable technology in most industrial complex systems. With the rapid development of information technology and sensor technology, the industry has become a data-rich environment, which provides opportunities for developing the data-driven fault diagnosis method to substitute time-consuming knowledge-based and rule-based methods, thus enhance

efficiency and applicability of fault diagnosis. In recent years, the fault diagnosis methods based on deep learning have been well studied and applied in large industrial system [2, 3, 5, 12, 16, 17].

However, the effectiveness of the advanced models can be guaranteed only existing enough data samples into the model during the training period. The capability of these deep models may be degraded dramatically when this assumption can not be satisfied. Unfortunately, in the real-world application, the gearbox needs to switch speed and load frequently according to the production demand. Usually, the machine would not run at high speed and load unless there is an emergency need, and it could not work with worrying fault. For this reason, the data coming from the heavy condition and sudden serious failure should be hard to collect, while the normal data are sufficient. This phenomenon is referred to as a few-shot fault diagnosis, in which training a model can generalize well only used one or a few data samples.

Recently, some researchers in the fault diagnosis field have paid attention to the few-shot fault diagnosis problem and proposed advanced methods to overcome the overfitting problem by training with limited data samples [1, 7, 14]. Although these methods are effective for the few-shot fault diagnosis tasks to a certain degree, they did not utilize the feature information of related diagnosis tasks as support for helping the current few-shot learning task. We try to deal with the few-shot fault diagnosis problem in the meta-learning perspective, which could with the help of the transferable knowledge learning from the source domain to address the few-shot diagnosis issue in the target domain.

In this paper, a Meta-learning guided Few-shot Fault Diagnosis framework, called MFFD, is presented for the gearbox fault diagnosis under different limited data conditions. The preliminaries is detailed in Section 2, and the theoretical framework is described in Section 3. Section 4 shows detailed experiments and analysis results. The conclusions has been made in Section 5.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Problem Definition

Fig. 1 (c) shows the few-shot fault diagnosis, the training and test data draw from the different domain, the target domain is the few-shot fault diagnosis task which has limited labeled samples, while the source domain owns sufficient data which is annotated but totally different with the target domain. The meta-learning method is to exploit the transferable knowledge by utilizing the episodic training mechanism for facilitating the model in a few-shot condition [9–11]. The target domain of few-shot fault diagnosis is defined as \mathcal{T}^T which has a C^T -way, K -shot, M -test task. In this task, there are an annotated support data set $\mathcal{S}^T : (x_{S_a}^T, y_{S_a}^T)_{a=1}^{N_S^T}$ and an unannotated query data set $\mathcal{Q}^T : (x_{Q_a}^T)_{a=1}^{N_Q^T}$. In our work, K is equal to 1 or 5, while M set to 25, x is the vibration signal sample and y is the label. Samples of auxiliary set in source domain are defined as $X^S = (x_a^S, y_a^S)_{a=1}^{N^S}$. The source domain has totally different failure categories C^S .

2.2 Metric-based Meta-learning

The metric-based meta-learning aims at addressing the few-shot learning problem with the set-to-set approach [4, 10], which can predict the labels for the unobservable categories without making any changes to the trained model. Specifically, the metric-based model is a probability distribution mapping $P(\hat{y}|\hat{x}, S)$ from the input samples \hat{x} to the output labels \hat{y} , while the $S = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^k$ is a support set of K labeled samples. When a new few-shot support set S' coming, the model will be directly use to output the label \hat{y} for each test sample \hat{x} : $P(\hat{y}|\hat{x}, S')$. The metric-based meta-learning model is defined in general as follows:

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha(\hat{x}, x_i) y_i, \quad (1)$$

where x_i, y_i draw from the support set $S = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^k$, and α is the metric-based attention kernel. Unlike the typical supervise learning model, the metric-based meta-learning is a non-parametric method and quickly adapts to any new support set.

Matching Networks As the initial method of metric-based meta-learning, Matching Networks [9] define a conditional classification model with the support set, which explicitly chooses the softmax over the cosine distance as the similarity function α for the few-shot test sample \hat{x} and the support sample x_i . The similarity kernel function is expressed as follows:

$$\alpha(\hat{x}, x_i; \theta) = \frac{\exp[d(f(\hat{x}), f(x_i))]}{\sum_{j=1}^k \exp[d(f(\hat{x}), f(x_j))]} \quad (2)$$

where the f is an appropriate neural network with parameter θ as the embedding function; d is a cosine distance function.

Prototypical Networks Prototypical Network [8] performance better than Matching Networks for solving the few-shot problem in the image classification field, which benefit from the idea that there should exist a single prototype representation for each class in the points cluster. The prototype representation is the mean vector of its belonging category, which can be calculated as follows:

$$c_k = \frac{1}{|S_k|} \sum_{x_j, y_i \in S_k} f(x_i), \quad (3)$$

where S_k denotes the set of examples labeled with class k in the given supporting set. With the changes in the Prototypical Networks, the similarity kernel will turn to

$$\alpha(\hat{x}, c_k; \theta) = \frac{\exp[d(f(\hat{x}), c_k)]}{\sum_{j=1}^k \exp[d(f(\hat{x}), c_k)]}, \quad (4)$$

where d denotes the Euclidean distance in such a method. Similar to the Matching Networks, the training process also aims at minimizing the negative log-probability $J(\theta) = -\log(P(y|x, S; \theta))$ through stochastic gradient descent (SGD).

3 Theoretical Framework

The framework of our proposed MFFD method is shown in Fig. 1 (a), which consists of three-part, including few-shot tasks sampling, embedding mapping, and matching classification. The data samples of the source domain are reformed to generate few-shot tasks for episode training. Then the support set S_i and the query set Q_i are input to embedding mapping, while the embedding mapping is optimized by the metric loss function L_m , which is defined in equation (9). After the training procedure, the embedding mapping is directly used to identify the test few-shot tasks from the unseen target domain.

Fig. 1. (a) Meta-learning guided Few-shot Fault Diagnosis (MFFD) framework; (b) Gearbox applications; (c) Few-shot fault diagnosis.

3.1 Embedding Mapping

For the fault diagnosis tasks, the vibration wave is the main signal to be processed, which is a typical one-dimensional signal. The embedding mapping is the critical term of our proposed method, which consist of several one-dimensional convolutional layers and a fully connected layer. More specifically, the one-dimensional convolutional layer is defined as follows:

$$C_{ij}^l = \phi(k_{n \times 1}^j * x_{i:i+n}^i + b_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

where, $k_{n \times 1}^j$ is the j th kernel which belong to the kernels K_j^l size $n \times 1 \times j$ of the l -th convolution layer; $x_{i:i+n}^i$ is the i th input segment; b_{ij} is corresponding to the bias; ϕ is the activation function; C_{ij}^l is the i -th feature point of the j -th kernel in the l -th convolution layer.

3.2 Episodic Learning Procedure

The metric embedding mapping is defined as $f_M(\cdot)$ with parameters θ_M . For implementing the episodic training, the data sampled of source domain will be randomly sampled to generate a range of few-shot learning tasks of fault diagnosis \mathcal{T}^S , in each of which there has C^S -way, K -shot, M -test and C^S don't need to equal C^T of \mathcal{T}^T in the target domain. The support set and the query set of source domain are defined as $\mathcal{S}^S = (x_{S_a}^S, y_{S_a}^S)_{a=1}^{N_S^S}$ and $\mathcal{Q}^S = (x_{Q_a}^S, y_{Q_a}^S)_{a=1}^{N_Q^S}$, respectively, where N_S^S equals to $C^T \times K$ and N_Q^S equals to M .

The core of our MFFD is to learn the transferable feature of embedding mapping from the source domain and directly use it to solve the few-shot fault diagnosis in the target domain. Therefore, after processing the data samples of the source domain, the classification performance of the query set by matching the feature of embedding mapping to the support set should be conducted. The one-dimensional raw fault signal x as the input for the embedding mapping, the prediction is calculated by the weighted sum of support labels, which is defined as follows (note that the superscripts S are omitted for simplicity):

$$\hat{y}_{Q_n} = \sum_{a=1}^{N_S} w[f_M(x_{Q_n}), f_M(x_{S_a})] \cdot y_{S_a} \quad (6)$$

where the w is the softmax normalization of distance, which is calculated by the distance between the feature of the query set and each support set:

$$w[f_M(b_{Q_n}), f_M(b_{S_a})] = \frac{\exp(-\tau * d[f_M(b_{Q_n}), f_M(b_{S_a})])}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_S} \exp(-\tau * d[f_M(b_{Q_n}), f_M(b_{S_j})])} \quad (7)$$

where τ is a hyper-parameter to control the convergence of training. The kernel function $d[\cdot]$ is defined as:

$$d[x_i, x_j] = \frac{x_i \cdot x_j^T}{|x_i||x_j|} \quad (8)$$

Finally, the objective for optimizing metric embedding mapping with parameter θ_M is defined as follows:

$$L_M(\theta_M) = \sum_{\mathcal{T}^S} L_M(\mathcal{T}^S; \theta_M) = \sum_{\mathcal{T}^S} \left[-\frac{1}{N_Q^S} \sum_{n=1}^{N_Q^S} \sum_{i=1}^{C^S} \mathbb{I}[y_{Q_n} = i] \cdot \log(\hat{y}_{Q_n}(i)) \right] \quad (9)$$

The above learning process is described following the Matching Network (MN). As the alternative way of Matching Network, Prototypical Network (PN) in our MFFD framework is defined as follows:

$$\hat{y}_{Q_n} = \sum_{a=1}^{C^S} w[f_M(b_{Q_n}), P_a^S] \cdot y_a \quad (10)$$

where P_a^S is the mean vector of embedding features of the a th category:

$$P_a^S = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{j \in a} f_M(b_{S_j}) \quad (11)$$

The calculation of weights and distance and training objective are similar to Eqs. (7), (8) and (9). In our MFFD, MN and PN versions are compared and analyzed.

3.3 The Workflow

In this section, The workflow of training strategy for our method is detailed as follows:

1. Data Processing: Reform the data samples of source domain X^S as the few-shot learning tasks $\{\mathcal{S}_i^S, \mathcal{Q}_i^S\}_{i=1}^n$;
2. Initialization: Initialize parameters of embedding mapping θ_M ;
3. Training: Input the few-shot tasks of source domain $\{\mathcal{S}_i^S, \mathcal{Q}_i^S\}_{i=1}^n$ to train the embedding mapping with the objective L_M , which can be expressed as:

$$\theta_M \leftarrow \theta_M - \alpha L_M; \quad (12)$$

4. Test: Input the query set \mathcal{Q}^T of the target domain to embedding mapping with trained parameters θ_M and limited labeled support set S^T .

4 Experiment

4.1 Data Preparation

A gearbox fault diagnosis dataset [13, 15] is utilized to testify our proposed method. The test rig is shown in Fig. 1 (b), an accelerometer is installed on the gearbox body closing to the drive shaft for collecting the 1D vibration signal. As shown in Table 1, there are six categories of gear failure: Normal, Chipped Tooth (CT), and Missing Tooth (MT), Bent Shaft (BS), Rotor Imbalance (RI), and Mixed fault with BS and MT. Each type has 500 samples of different speeds (30, 35, 40, 45 and 50 Hz) and different loads (Low and High). The sampling frequency is 66.67 kHz and every input data has 6600 points.

4.2 Experimental Setup

Few-shot Setup for Fault Diagnosis In the few-shot fault diagnosis experiments, the source domain has enough labeled dataset $D^s = \{x_i^s, y_i^s\}_{i=1}^{n^s}$, and the target domain is part of Support dataset $S^t = \{x_k^t, y_k^t\}_{k=1}^K$ and the test task dataset $D^t = \{x_j^t\}_{j=1}^{n^t}$. It is for sure that the fault types of the supporting dataset would not be seen in the source domain, and the task dataset is unlabeled. One-shot means only 1 sample of each category in the support set, while five-shot denote 5 samples in the support set.

Table 1. Description of gearbox dataset

Fault location	Normal	CT	MT	BS	RI	Mix	Speed	Load
Category Labels	0	1	2	3	4	5		
Dataset 30L no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	30Hz	Low
Dataset 30H no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	30Hz	High
Dataset 35L no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	35Hz	Low
Dataset 35H no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	35Hz	High
Dataset 40L no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	40Hz	Low
Dataset 40H no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	40Hz	High
Dataset 45L no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	45Hz	Low
Dataset 45H no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	45Hz	High
Dataset 50L no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	50Hz	Low
Dataset 50H no.	500	500	500	500	500	500	50Hz	High

In this work, we mainly evaluate our model in the following two scenarios: 1) The source and target domain draw from the different working conditions for 1-shot and 5-shot learning fault diagnosis situations; 2) The source and target domain from the different categories under the same working condition for 1-shot and 5-shot learning fault diagnosis situations.

Compared Methods All the few-shot tasks is compared with several few-shot learning methods for comparing with our proposed method, which is detailed as follow:

1. Finetune Last:
2. Fintune Whole:
3. Feature Knn:
4. Feature Knn Proto:
5. MFFD-MN
6. MFFD-PN

1) to 3) are based on pre-training the embedding mapping and the last classifier with source domain data with supervised learning. 1) and 2) are designed to finetune the classifier or the whole model by utilizing the few-shot data from the target domain; 3) and 4) compare the abstracted features with those of support samples by few-shot data of target domain; 5) and 6) are the Matching Network and Prototypical Network model with embedding mapping as the backbone in raw data space.

Implementation Details The detail of network architecture is shown in Table 2. Adam optimization is used to train, and all models are trained for the labeled source domain is close 100% before used for the target domain. The number of iterations is 100 and the learning rate is 0.001 in Finetune Last and Whole models. Cosine distance is utilized in the KNN model. In meta-learning methods, the number of query samples is 25, the maximum training epochs is 100. The

query samples generally decided on the capacity of GPU memory, but it suggests to large than the number of support samples. All the experiments had been tested on the computer with GPU of Nvidia GeForce GTX 2060 6GB and CPU of Intel Core i7-10750H of 2.60 GHz.

Table 2. Details of Network Architecture

Components	Layer type	Kernel	Stride	Channels	Padding
Embedding Mapping	Convolution 1	64×1	16×1	16	No
	ReLU 1				
	Max Pooling 1	2×1	2×1	16	No
	Convolution 2	3×1	1×1	32	Yes
	ReLU 2				
	Max Pooling 2	2×1	2×1	32	No
	Convolution 3	3×1	1×1	64	Yes
	ReLU 3				
	Max Pooling 3	2×1	2×1	64	No
	Convolution 4	3×1	1×1	64	Yes
	ReLU 4				
	Max Pooling 4	2×1	2×1	64	No
	Convolution 5	3×1	1×1	64	Yes
	ReLU 5				

4.3 Result and Analysis

The few-shot fault diagnosis between different speed and load conditions including one-shot and five-shot learning tasks have been carried out, the experimental results are shown in Table 3. These results illustrate that our MFFD method performs best compared with other advanced baseline methods for all the few-shot tasks. Results of five-shot tasks generally better than the one-shot tasks mean that increasing the number of data samples will notably improve the performance of our model. MFFD with PN is better than MFFD with MN in most cases, but the number of samples for every category of support set is a more critical determinant. Limited by the PN mechanism, the PN based method only tested on five-shot situations.

Then, we test different methods on one-shot and five-shot learning tasks under different categories of the same conditions. In this case, there are two kinds of fault type as the few-shot tasks of the target domain, CT and MT, respectively. In CT, we assume that the chipped tooth and normal data samples are limited, while the missing tooth and normal data are limited in MT. Therefore, in this part of gearbox experiments, all the few-shot fault diagnosis tasks have 5 categories in the source domain in terms of training and 2 categories in the target domain waiting for testing. The results are shown in Table 4, the MFFD performs best at the majority of cases, and an interesting phenomenon is revealed which is that all the accuracies of MT are higher than the CT. We

Table 3. Accuracy (%) on one-shot and five-shot learning tasks for gearbox fault diagnosis with different working conditions

	30L→35H		30L→40H		30L→50L	
	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot
Finetune last	40.77	45.53	36.27	36.82	32.24	34.18
Fintune whole	44.43	51.87	39.33	46.34	37.50	43.29
Feature knn	61.21	69.20	49.40	52.93	44.67	50.76
MFFD-MN	85.48	87.63	84.23	89.25	84.87	86.64
Feature Knn Proto	*	67.58	*	58.99	*	58.04
MFFD-PN	*	87.51	*	90.22	*	88.49
	40L→45L		40L→50L		40L→45H	
	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot
Finetune last	50.06	52.73	49.53	52.61	50.06	52.73
Fintune whole	50.08	61.05	51.03	62.65	50.08	61.05
Feature knn	61.49	66.80	68.76	75.87	61.49	66.80
MFFD-MN	65.33	72.04	83.94	89.23	65.32	70.04
Feature Knn Proto	*	58.80	*	63.91	*	58.80
MFFD-PN	*	75.85	*	80.20	*	75.85

believe that the training data of the source domain in MT is more difficult to identify than the task in CT, then the embedding network will be learned much better, therefore, it can offer more transferable information for supporting the target few-shot learning tasks.

In summary, comparing with other state-of-the-art methods, our MFFD model performs best on all one-shot and five-shot tasks for the gearbox fault diagnosis under multiple limited data conditions. The PN-based MFFD is verified better than the MN-based MFFD in certain circumstances.

4.4 Visualization Analysis

The t-SNE [6] has been used to visualize the embedding mapping for analyzing the results of our MFFD method. The visualization of two-dimensional results are displayed in Figure 2, different colour denotes different failure categories. The results of MFFD demonstrate that the embedding feature of the same category is placed at the closed area and the feature from different fault types is clearly distinguished in the source domain, which means that the model is trained well in the source domain. However, some fault types in the target domain are interacted with different type, while most of the fault is notably separable. These results verify that our MFFD method can really utilize the transferable knowledge learning from the source domain to deal with the few-shot learning tasks in the target domain. All in all, we can confirm that our MFFD method has very remarkably effective to overcome the few-shot fault diagnosis problem for gearbox under various limited data conditions.

Table 4. Accuracy (%) on one-shot and five-shot learning tasks for gearbox fault with different categories under same conditions

	30L		30H		40L	
	CT	MT	CT	MT	CT	MT
One-shot						
Finetune Last	88.46	93.96	64.38	93.12	97.16	91.58
Finetune Whole	77.98	90.96	64.22	95.82	76.02	93.54
Feature Knn	91.7	100.00	71.38	100.00	99.66	100.00
MFFD-MN	85.08	100.00	65.84	100.00	99.84	100.00
Five-shot						
Finetune Last	87.80	99.36	75.60	93.88	98.98	92.18
Finetune Whole	89.12	96.62	79.30	99.36	90.22	96.36
Feature Knn	90.52	100.00	82.74	100.00	99.70	100.00
MFFD-MN	90.64	100.00	90.22	100.00	99.80	100.00
Feature Knn Proto	84.18	100.00	78.02	100.00	99.78	100.00
MFFD-PN	86.90	100.00	92.06	100.00	99.94	100.00
	40H		50L		50H	
	CT	MT	CT	MT	CT	MT
One-shot						
Finetune Last	89.04	95.78	94.92	80.3	87.68	89.68
Finetune Whole	80.82	97.00	79.26	74.92	72.46	96.74
Feature Knn	93.68	100.00	99.76	100.00	94.10	100.00
MFFD-MN	99.22	100.00	100.00	100.00	97.80	100.00
Five-shot						
Finetune Last	96.02	97.06	98.76	86.22	94.04	90.90
Finetune Whole	93.38	99.60	93.08	90.30	84.86	99.72
Feature Knn	95.24	100.00	99.98	100.00	96.84	100.00
MFFD-MN	96.90	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.14	100.00
Feature Knn Proto	96.88	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.14	100.00
MFFD-PN	97.20	100.00	100.00	100.00	94.92	100.00

5 Conclusion

In this work, a novel Meta-Learning guided Few-shot Fault Diagnosis framework, named MFFD, to address the few-shot learning problem for gearbox fault diagnosis under various limited data conditions has been proposed and verified. The essence of our work is to learn the transferable knowledge from the source domain, then making the trained model with a support set able to directly identify the fault types in the target domain. Experimental and Visualized results on one-shot and five-shot tasks of the gearbox fault diagnosis indicate that MFFD performs better than other advanced methods.

Fig. 2. t-SNE visualization of gearbox data features embedding derived from the MFFD. (a), (b) and (c) denote results of MFFD-MN 1-shot, MFFD-MN 5-shot and MFFD-PN 5-shot respectively for the 30L→40H task. (d), (e) and (f) denote results of MFFD-MN 1-shot, MFFD-MN 5-shot and MFFD-PN 5-shot respectively for the Chipped Tooth (CT) fault task under the condition of 30Hz low load. For each sub-figure, the up figure denotes the data feature from the source domain and the down figure denotes the data feature from the target domain.

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